

Rethinking active learning program for primary English teachers through connoisseurship technique

Nippita Kulachit, Prasart Nuangchalerm
Faculty of Education, Mahasarakham University, Thailand

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ABSTRACT

From the importance of English in world of internationally communicated, the problems of learning management in each area seems to be differenced, language and culture are needed for recognizing, active learning is called for effectiveness instruction, and primary English teachers need to prepared in modern classroom. This research employed evaluative research to employ active learning for primary English teachers through professional program. Data were collected by setting a connoisseurship technique. Seven experts are appointed and read carefully a tentative program for primary English teachers. The connoisseurship technique allowed all experts share their experiences and ideas to promote active learning in freely. Video recording and note taking were recorded during the validation activity. Active learning program for primary English teachers is approved before implementation in different school contexts. The uncertainty situations, COVID-19 pandemic may be affected to schooling, teachers have to redesign lesson. The implementation though active online learning is needed to discuss and rethinking how it be effectively in authentic classroom.

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Corresponding Author:

Prasart Nuangchalerm
Faculty of Education
Mahasarakham University
Mahasarakham 44000, Thailand
Email: prasart.n@msu.ac.th

1. INTRODUCTION

In an era when the world is unified without borders, communication and exchange of information and with people all over the world has expanded rapidly. These have affected changes in the learning environment and lifestyle. This situation is therefore a huge challenge for today's instructors and uncertainty learning environment [1]-[3]. The need to develop learners to keep up with the changes and be ready to deal with the world in the new era. Therefore, we cannot deny that English is of little importance because English is a universal mediated tool used to communicate [4]-[6]. To build understanding of the cultures of different countries, learners must understand the vision of individual ethnicities. The concept of learning management for 21st century learners has changed, with the need for the necessary skills including communication, collaboration, and creativity [7], [8].

Instructors must focus on these attributes so that they have knowledge, skills and desirable attributes that can be used to solve problems, as well as have the discretion to communicate and receive information. These issues are important to be expedited for all learners in the relation of language and culture awareness because it is the need of today's global society [9], [10]. It is very important to improve learning ability to use English in particular. English speaking ability for learners to be higher and more efficient are required for open the world of learning. Language and culture can be transferred through suitable and productive teaching

by professional teachers. However, teaching English in this era is not difficult, but more fun with learning language through technology-enhanced learning.

Learning management in English courses in Thailand has always been a problem. This is especially true in English speaking, which seems to be the most difficult for learners. There are several reasons that learners have a negative attitude towards learning English. Learners less motivation in communication and do not dare to speak English with other people. Also, they less confidence in speaking English by mean of strange language or hard to communicate in non-real life situations. There is not enough knowledge basis to speak English, less of interaction in the learning management process with other learners in the classroom, and the instructor less a learning management process that can help learners promoting the learner's ability to speak English [11]-[13]. Most teachers still stick to narrative learning arrangements, or traditional learning activities are employed by reproductive lesson by passive instruction into classroom.

Learning management in new era of information technology disruption, development of speaking English simply by aiming to provide learners with the right English language and meaning. focusing on providing them with good and accurate pronunciation to achieve indicators in learning [14], [15]. The choice of language, tone and gestures suits the level of persons, occasions and places according to the manners, society and culture of native speakers. Basic education management operations of Educational Institutions under the Office of the Basic Education Commission launched the integration plan to some schools have not improved their learning management processes to be connected and aligned. Learning standards and indicators based on the core curriculum of basic education. It is not possible to reflect the teaching process concretely and clearly, which may affect the effectiveness of teaching and improving the quality of education [16], [17].

The implementation of guidelines aims to promote the production and development of quality teachers, educational personnel has not met the specified objectives. English teachers trained under the regional English Core Teacher Development Program have not adopted English teaching techniques in accordance with the guidelines. Communicative Approach has been trained for teaching and learning. Schools and teachers focus on teaching and learning for exams, so they also use traditional teaching rather than focusing on communication skills, teaching processes or techniques is not adapted to learners, leaving learners in short of opportunities to develop or practice their English communication skills [15], [18].

Traditional learning management behaviors that do not prepare teaching/preparing teaching but do not teach according to the prepared plan. Study standards and indicators are not comprehensive, so the teaching and learning arrangements do not cover a wide range of learning activities. Activities that promote the self-knowledge creation of minority learners. Learners are less engaged in learning activities, less interact with each other. Primary English teachers in low learning rarely find activities to promote and improve thinking skills, less active learning, and the self-improvement. They also had difficulty managing learning to promote and develop thinking skills towards a wide range of advanced thinking. Activities to encourage learners to participate in learning and self-knowledge creation.

From problems and self-improvement needs in English teachers, also the previous report by Kulachit and Nuangchalerm [19] found that teachers need to improve their instructional practices through the active learning. Instructors are required to create or develop effective learning management processes as well as learning environment. Encouraging learners to develop their ability to use English effectively, teachers have rethink about how to implement innovative teaching via technology or various kind of teaching strategies [20]. Learners can do the high potential of learning experience, the success of speaking English, and meet the requirement of learning opportunity in language barriers.

It must be an interesting learning arrangement that is conducive to learning learners so that they are alert to participate in activities. Active learning as a possible in language learning successful, and building as much knowledge as it be. Active learning is a constructivism concept that emphasizes the opportunity for learners to play the most important role in the learning management process. Learning experience gather information and summarize variety of interesting by diversity of learning management activities. Learners encourage to apply their existing knowledge and experiences and connect new knowledge from having interaction in learning together to create self-knowledge [21]. Active learning is a variety of learning management methods and techniques used to plan learning management and organize learning activities that can encourage and encourage learners to participate in the creation.

Additionally, there is too much research reported that active learning is a learning management approach where learners learn more. Learners can create their own knowledge based on learning management process that focuses on engaging in learning activities and promoting learning together as a group [22]. The important aspects of the learning management process help to promote English proficiency for the learner. From the importance of English and the problems of learning management, learning the effectiveness of active learning, and needs of primary English teachers mentioned above. It is essential to develop courses to promote proactive learning management for teaching primary English to be

knowledgeable. The research employed evaluative research to response the active learning program for primary English teachers intended outcomes and the participants of the program employable before it starts.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed evaluative research to assess active learning program for primary English teachers. The program was developed through the empirical data and document analysis as its report by Kulachit and Nuangchalerm [19]. Teachers required program to enhance their ability to design lesson based on active learning management is at high level. The most considering the list, the three highest average number of items is that they need to develop active learning management; need having active knowledge in learning management; and need primary basic English knowledge are guideline for tentative program.

Workshop and training in the collaborative paradigm is invited to the program, they are ready to join the active learning program as well as disruptive education. The training might want to have the production of media, teaching strategies, and other techniques to scaffolding students in various kinds of methods. Program is developed through the surveying methods and synthesized related concepts. Then, it is validated by seven experts from fields of educational research and professional development.

Data were collected by setting a connoisseurship technique. Seven experts are appointed and read carefully a tentative program for primary English teachers. The connoisseurship technique allowed all experts share their experiences and ideas to promote active learning freely. Video recording and note taking were recorded during the validation activity. Finally, all of experts rated their opinion towards the program in the dimension of its appropriateness. Researchers concluded and reported to all experts in valuable suggestions, revision program to be authentic, and approved before program implementation as soon. Data were analyzed by descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation. The level of appropriateness of professional development program can be calculated and interpreted by indicating into five levels of mean for interpreting: highest (4.51-5.00), high (3.51-4.50), medium (2.51-3.50), low (1.51-2.50), and lowest (1.00-1.50).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Active learning program for primary English teachers is developed through the previous study by Kulachit and Nuangchalerm [19]. Program rethinks about how to motivate primary English teachers engage learners in active classroom activities. The program is tentative guide from document analysis and empirical survey report. A professional development program looks beyond how primary English teachers design and implement active learning into different school contexts. The program is drawn and described its components in Table 1 promotes knowledge and understanding of active learning management for primary school English teachers.

Table 1. Active learning program for primary English teachers

Principles		Objectives	
1. Promotes knowledge and understanding of active learning management for primary English teachers.		1. To provide primary English teachers knowledge and understanding of active learning management.	
2. Promotes the ability to design active learning management plans for primary English teachers.		2. To provide primary English teachers with the ability to design active learning management plans.	
3. Promotes active learning management capabilities for primary English teachers.		3. To provide primary English teachers with the ability to actively manage to learn.	
Contents			
Content/subject matter includes: knowledge of foreign language learning subjects (emphasizing English), active learning management practices, active learning management design, active measurement and evaluation, and active learning management capabilities. This requires primary school English teachers participating in development to learn and be encouraged to be cognitive and actively manage to learn.			
Unit	Content	Time (hour)	
	Learning area of foreign languages	Theory	Practice
1	The basic education core curriculum and learning area of foreign languages	1	2
2	Active learning: theory, practice, and application	1	2
3	Lesson design and active learning management	3	9
Classroom observation, monitoring, and professional learning community on school site visit		-	10-12

The program is set by 10:20:70 which can be explained that 10% by the above program, running by face to face workshop on active learning management. Following by 20%, primary English teachers will meet peers or experts, classroom observation, monitoring, and professional learning community on school

site visit are conducted. Finally, 70% of learning, teachers learn how manage their instructional practices based on active learning in English subject by themselves [23]-[25]. They will construct knowledge and understanding through learning by doing in suitable school contexts. Finding from the connoisseurship technique revealed that the program for primary English teachers is at ranges high to highest level, but different in each issue. The evidence from their opinion can be concluded in Table 2.

Table 2. Appropriateness of active learning program for primary English teachers

Item	\bar{x}	SD	Level of appropriateness
1. Program principles	4.04	0.44	High
1.1 reasonable	4.29	0.49	High
1.2 concurrent with conditions and practical	4.14	0.69	High
1.3 improve the school curriculum	4.14	0.38	High
1.4 theoretical concepts supported	3.57	0.98	High
2. Program objectives	4.43	0.37	High
2.1 be clear	4.57	0.79	Highest
2.2 covers goals	4.57	0.53	Highest
2.3 possible to use	4.29	0.49	High
2.4 suitable for target audiences	4.29	0.49	High
3. Program materials	4.11	0.50	High
3.1 complies with program destinations	4.29	0.49	High
3.2 covers program destinations	4.00	0.82	High
3.3 content meets the requirements.	4.00	0.58	High
3.4 contents sequences	4.14	0.38	High
4. Program execution method	4.39	0.24	High
4.1 consistent and comprehensive with program destinations	4.57	0.53	Highest
4.2 properly sorted in the order of developmental steps	4.43	0.53	High
4.3 fulfillment program	4.57	0.53	Highest
4.4 suitable for target audience and duration	4.00	0.00	High
5. Media & program documentation	4.39	0.24	High
5.1 complies with program destinations	4.57	0.53	Highest
5.2 properly sorted in the order to developmental step	4.43	0.53	High
5.3 fulfillment of the program goals	4.57	0.53	Highest
5.4 suitable for target audience and duration	4.00	0.00	High
6. Program evaluation	4.29	0.30	High
6.1 complies with program destinations	4.57	0.53	Highest
6.2 covers the criteria for evaluation	4.57	0.53	Highest
6.3 concurrent with program attainment	4.00	0.58	High
6.4 suitable for target audience and duration	4.00	0.00	High
Overall	4.28	0.73	High

It shows that active learning program for primary English teachers as a whole, it is very suitable for teacher development ($\bar{x}=4.28$, $SD=0.73$). When considering the individual elements, the six elements are suitable at a high level in all elements. Sort descending as follows: program objectives ($\bar{x}=4.43$, $SD=0.37$), program execution method ($\bar{x}=4.43$, $S.D=0.37$), media & program documentation ($\bar{x}=4.43$, $SD=0.37$), program evaluation ($\bar{x}=4.29$, $SD=0.30$), program materials ($\bar{x}=4.11$, $SD=0.50$) and program principles ($\bar{x}=4.04$, $S.D=0.44$) in respectively. The 7 experts' opinions can be summarized through qualitative report in the following: i) Revise objectives of the program from "promote" to "give teachers"; ii) Principles should be revised by combining introductions and principles into one text; iii) Principles of active learning management should be summarized according to teachers' implication; iv) Each unit of learning should provide the method or process active learning management; v) Specify the role of researchers and teachers in clearly as its happens in the manual guide; vi) Provide examples of active learning management lesson plan in the manual guide; and vii) Measurement and evaluation instruments should also be shown in the manual guide.

The evaluative research also known as program evaluation, which this study employed as techniques to validate the program for primary English teachers. The experts' opinions are valuable for constructive knowledge and more understanding how to improve program in the better ways. Evaluation research requires participants to keep in mind the interests of program stakeholders. The meaningful information will be produced from the experiences' experts, they will provide valuable insights to program development in better decision-making [26].

Program is validated, rethink its operations in the professional development, active learning management is revised, and appropriateness of program is evaluated in both quantitative and qualitative methods. Program for primary English teachers lets teacher understand about how to think and do active learning in their school contexts. They can find out the areas of teaching improvement especially the new era of technology-enhanced learning and school at risk. Teachers have self-development through active learning workshop which is set by educational supervisor, then learn from peer or professional learning community.

Rethinking active learning program for primary English teachers through ... (Nippita Kulachit)

However, active learning will be accomplished by professional experiences [27], [28]. Professional development program is approved by experts, it ready for implementation as well. While the uncertainty situations, COVID-19 pandemic may be affected to schooling, teachers have to redesign lesson which is suitable in their instructional practices [29], [30].

Rethinking active learning for primary English teachers, the previous conceptions of teachers are quite understand that it is instructional model and teaching methods. However, the finding showed that teachers rethink about active learning is approach or instructional design which allowing students learn by actively engaged in classroom. The program for English teachers is revised and flexible to professional development by 10:20:70 which can be explained by learning face to face workshop: learning from meet peers or experts: learning from self-development. The content and process of English can be emerged from teacher's empowerment in their authentic classroom.

4. CONCLUSION

Active learning program for primary English teachers is developed and rethinks about its effective in the field study. The program is set by 10:20:70 which can be explained that 10% by learning through face to face workshop on active learning management, 20% by learning from meet peers or experts, classroom observation, monitoring, and professional learning community, and 70% by learning from self-development and instructional practices. Rethinking about program for primary English teachers is revised and prepared for implementation, ready to design and implementation in school practices. However, the uncertainty of situations, COVID-19 pandemic may be affected to schooling, teachers have to redesign lesson. The implementation though active online learning is needed to discuss and rethinking how it be effectively in authentic classroom.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nippita Kulachit is an educational supervisor. She has been working for Kalasin Primary Education Service Area Office 1, Kalasin province in Thailand. Her research focuses on teacher development, active learning, and professional development.

Dr. Prasart Nuangchalem is an associate professor of curriculum and instruction. He has been working for Faculty of Education, Mahasarakham University in Thailand. His research focuses on teacher education, inquiry-based learning, pedagogical content knowledge, science teaching, and professional development.